

Array factor directivity for interference scenarios

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Abstract— The concept of array factor directivity is revised in order to propose a new well-suited definition for scenarios dominated by interference. A novel directivity measure is proposed including the interference that is caused to un-intended receivers. The new measure is properly bounded and, at the same time, it introduces the notion of retro-directivity in the design of antenna arrays. In addition, the beamformer that maximizes the new directivity measure is reported, proving that it never presents retro-directivity.

Keywords—Array factor, beamforming, directivity, interference, retro-directivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE directivity of a planar aperture at a given direction, which depends on the elevation and azimuth angles (θ, φ) , is defined as the field intensity in such direction at a distance r divided by the power density of an omnidirectional antenna radiating the same power at the same distance [1].

$$D(\theta, \varphi) = \frac{P(\theta, \varphi, r)}{P_{\text{rad}} / 4\pi r^2} \quad (1)$$

Note that under this definition, the directivity has dimension of surface, i.e. m^2 . Also, note that, although there is not any problem for its use both in the far as well as in the near field, developing this definition in the far field is easier than in the near field. In fact, for the far field, the directivity is always proportional to a factor depending on the field in the aperture as it is shown in (2).

$$D(\theta, \varphi) \propto \frac{\left| \int_A E(x, y) e^{j2\pi(xa_1 + ya_2)/\lambda} dx dy \right|^2}{\int_A |E(x, y)|^2 dx dy}$$

where

$$a_1 = \sin(\theta) \cos(\varphi) \quad a_2 = \sin(\theta) \sin(\varphi) \quad (2)$$

The effective area of the aperture surface bounds this last factor.

$$D(\theta, \varphi) \leq \frac{4\pi A_0}{\lambda^2} \quad (3)$$

Since A_0 denotes the area of the aperture, it can be said that the maximum of the directivity is bounded by 4π times the area of the aperture in square wavelengths.

Focusing on the case of planar antenna arrays, the factor affecting the directivity is shown in (4), where: $b(m)$ are the beamformer coefficients controlling the current at every antenna element, d_m is the radius, with respect to the phase center of the aperture in wavelengths, and φ_m is the azimuth location of antenna element m within the aperture [1]-[2].

$$D(\theta, \varphi) \propto \frac{\left| \sum_m b(m) \exp(j2\pi d_m \cos(\varphi - \varphi_m) \sin(\theta)) \right|^2}{\sum_m |b(m)|^2} \quad (4)$$

This factor is denoted as the array factor directivity. The array factor depends only on the geometry and the relative excitation to every antenna element in the aperture.

The rest of this paper focuses on how to modify (4) for scenarios where unintended receivers are present.

The main objective of the paper is to put emphasis on the fact that any of the existing definitions for array factor directivity are done disregarding the interference caused to other receivers in the scenario (see [3]-[5] as examples). However, currently, most communication scenarios are moving from noise dominated to interference dominated. Since proper transmitter antenna beamforming, or design, implies the optimization of the array factor directivity, it is evident that for scenarios dominated by interference the traditional definition is becoming obsolete. Note that to control the interference, the transmitter should have information about the location or spatial signatures for the unintended receiver locations. This information or knowledge is denoted as channel state information at the transmitter (CSIT).

The structure of the paper is: Section II.A reviews the traditional notion of directivity described in this section.

This work was supported in part by the Generalitat of Catalunya (Grant 2014SGR1567) and the EU (Projects SANSa) and ESA (SATNEX), and from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness TEC2014-59255-C3-1-R.

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Section II.B describes how directivity has been defined for scenarios dominated by interference, as well as the optimum beamforming policy to maximize the newly defined directivities. Section III introduces the notion of retro-directivity for interference-dominated scenarios. Section IV describes a new array factor directivity based on retro-directivity that overcomes the problems of the measures described in the previous section. Finally, Section V includes simulations to provide evidence of the superiority of the proposed directivity. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. ARRAY FACTOR DIRECTIVITY

This section will revisit the two current definitions of antenna array factor directivity, with emphasis on its suitability for interference scenarios. Along the paper, vectors are underlined and matrixes doubled underlined. Vector $\underline{\mathbf{b}}$ will denote the beamformer. The sub-indexes “d” and “i” will refer to desired location and interfered location respectively; in consequence $\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d$ and $\underline{\mathbf{h}}_q$ represent the channel response from the transmitter array to the desired or intended location and the channel to the un-intended or interfered location “q” respectively. Note that the above channel vectors are the spatial signatures of the transmitting array in a given location and they will coincide with the steering vector in a pure line of sight (LOS) propagation scenario. The angular dependency of the array factor on the elevation (linear arrays) or elevation/azimuth (2-D dimensional or 3-Dimensional arrays) will be omitted in the formulas for the sake of presentation.

A. Traditional Array Factor directivity

The most popular array factor directivity measure assumes LOS propagation and it is defined as the quotient between the response of the array factor at a giving direction, i.e. the intended or desired direction characterized by the steering vector $\underline{\mathbf{S}}_d$, divided by the power density (power/surface) radiated by a single omni-directional that uses the same power that the antenna array. The latter power is given by the norm of the beamformer in use. This popular definition of array factor directivity is shown in (5).

$$D_{ANT} = \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{S}}_d|^2}{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}|^2} \quad (5)$$

Note that this definition refers to direction and not location and, of course does not reflects the possibility of interference to un-intended locations. When refereeing to a desired location it is usual to mimic (5) just replacing the steering vector by the spatial signature of the desired location as it is shown in (6).

$$D_{IFA} = \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}|^2} \quad (6)$$

It is easy to check that this array factor directivity is always in the range between zero and the squared norm of the location vector $\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d$.

This array factor directivity does not consider the negative impact of un-intended locations, i.e. interference dominated scenarios.

The beamformer that maximizes (6) is the so-called matched beamformer (MF), which is the desired location vector with norm equal to one.

$$\underline{\mathbf{b}} = \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d / |\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d| \quad (7)$$

Finally, it is worth comment that an omnidirectional antenna does not exist in practice. Nevertheless, note that the denominator in (6) is not merely a normalization factor.

B. The Virtual Signal to Interference plus Noise ratio (VSNR) directivity factor

The traditional alternative to the previous definition D_{TRA} of array factor directivity is the so-called VSNR directivity. The definition is shown in (8), where NI unintended locations contribute to the denominator term with their respective location vectors, grouped in a single matrix in the second term of this formula.

$$D_{VSNR} = \frac{P_T |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}|^2 + P_T \sum_{q=1}^{NI} |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_{iq}|^2} = \frac{P_T |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}|^2 + P_T \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_i \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \quad (8)$$

The justification of this formula is somehow quite artificial. Basically, this justification is based on the definition of signal to noise ratio (SNR) at intended location plus a “virtual” interference term. The so-called virtual SNR that we define bellow.

The desired receiver experiences the power from the transmitter and its own noise power. This SNR is transformed in by the addition in the denominator of the virtual interference term (it does not exists in practice). This term is formed by the interference caused to the un-intended locations accumulated in a VSNR as show in (9). Where P_T is the available power at transmission referred to the noise power of the receiver. Note that the definition of P_T entails that the norm of the beamformer has to be one.

$$VSNR = \frac{P_T |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{1 + P_T \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_i \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \quad (9)$$

After (9), which is really a virtual SINR, since any directivity measure cannot change with the beamformer norm; the one in the denominator of (9) is just changed by the norm of the beamvector. Finally D_{VSNR} takes its usual form as (10).

$$D_{VSNR} = \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{(1/P_T) |\underline{\mathbf{b}}|^2 + \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_i \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \quad (10)$$

Several conceptual changes are in (9) with respect to the traditional version of directivity D_{TRA} . First, note that D_{VSNR} depends on the used power for transmission since there is no other way to reflect the amount of interference caused to the un-intended locations. As a consequence, this power, being referred to the noise of the intended receiver depends also on the receiver that is used. In summary, we may say that all the propagation-rooted arguments to derive D_{TRA} have disappeared in favor of communications arguments. This is the

case of the beamformer norm that in (9) is more normalization factor than before in (6).

The beamformer that maximizes the Rayleigh quotient (10) is the so-called VSNR beamformer, which is the maximum generalized eigenvalue of the quadratic form in the numerator and in the denominator respectively. This beamvector is shown in (11.a), where parameter ϕ normalizes to one the norm of the beamvector. When the numerator is a quadratic form of a rank-one matrix, the generalized eigenvalue has the closed form in (11.a).

$$\underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\text{VSNR}} = \phi \left(\frac{1}{P_T} \underline{\mathbf{I}} + \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \right)^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d \quad (11.a)$$

$$D_{\text{VSNR}}^{\text{MAX}} = \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d \left(\frac{1}{P_T} \underline{\mathbf{I}} + \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \right)^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d \quad (11.b)$$

The bounds of this directivity measure are zero and (12), which is directly derived from (11.b).

$$D_{\text{VSNR}}^{\text{MAX}} \leq |\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2 \left(P_T^{-1} + \lambda_{\min}(\underline{\mathbf{R}}_I) \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

When the number of antennas n_T is greater than the number of interfered location N_I , the interfered matrix is rank deficient and its minimum eigenvalue is zero, thus (13) is the upper bound of this array factor directivity. This maximum is achieved when the desired is in the null-subspace of the interference matrix.

$$D_{\text{VSNR}}^{\text{MAX}} \leq P_T |\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2 \quad (13)$$

Before living this section it is important to remark that D_{VSNR} does not penalize the fact that the interference power could be higher than the power delivered to the desired. Furthermore, for the scenario where all the interference locations coincide with the desired one, the directivity is given by (14), which evidently, is greater than zero.

$$D_{\text{VSNR}} \Big|_{N_I=1, \text{ at } \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d=\underline{\mathbf{h}}_i} = \left(P_T |\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2 \right) / \left(P_T n_T |\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2 + 1 \right) \quad (14)$$

This problem is linked to the retro-directivity concept, as it will be shown in the next section.

It is also worth remark that in order to compare this directivity, which depends on the used power P_T , with the traditional definition (6), it is necessary to set the power equal to one. Doing this the bounds of the two directivities are the same.

III. RETRO-DIRECTIVITY

The notion of retro-directivity or negative directivity comes from the assumption that a proper array factor should devote more power to the intended location than the interference promoted to the un-intended locations.

The first attempt to reflect retro-directivity is to compare the difference in terms of traditional directivity to the intended and un-intended locations. Since directivity is expressed in dB, the difference reduces to the quotient of the two directivities, as it is shown in (15).

$$D_{\text{RD}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{b}}|^2} \right) - 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \underline{\mathbf{b}}}{\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$D_{\text{RD}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \right)$$

When the number of unintended locations is greater than the number of antenna, the beamformer that maximizes this directivity is given by (16.a). On the other hand, when the number of unintended locations is less than the number of antennas for transmission, the solution is the so-called Zero-Forcing (ZF) beamforming (16.b). The beamformer (16.b), for rank deficient interference matrix, nulls out the interference in all unintended locations. Parameter ϕ ensures that the norm of the beamformer is one for both cases.

$$\underline{\mathbf{b}} = \phi \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d \quad (16.a)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\text{ZF}} = \phi \left(\underline{\mathbf{I}} - \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}_I^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \right)^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I^H \right) \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d \quad (16.b)$$

Note that this directivity is independent of the used power as it is the case for the traditional definition.

It is important to check the bounds of this directivity. There is no upper bound for D_{RDA} since, for rank deficient interference matrix, this directivity is unbounded. On the other hand, when the unintended locations are all of them at the intended location this directivity is negative. It seems reasonable that for this case any directivity instead of negative should be zero. This implies to define the directivity in terms of the average interference power instead of the global power, as it is indicated in (17). The number of unintended locations is N_I .

$$D_{\text{RDA}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{N_I |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \right) \quad (17)$$

The major problem for the ZF beamformer is that for closed intended/unintended locations, forcing the null to the unintended precludes significant levels of power at the intended location. This results in a waste of the used power for transmission. This is a serious problem for limited available power for transmission. In addition, the unbounded character of this measure should be considered as a problem.

Next section suggests a new directivity measure, which overcomes both problems.

IV. NEW ARRAY FACTOR DIRECTIVITY

The new definition is rooted in the VSNR and it introduces the retro-directivity at its numerator. Solving, as it will be shown hereafter, it solves the problems associated with the D_{VSNR} definition. The new directivity is called D_{RD} and it is defined as (18).

$$D_{\text{RD}} = \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2 - \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \underline{\mathbf{b}}}{P_T^{-1} |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{b}}| + \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{with } \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I = \frac{1}{N_I} \sum_{q=1}^{N_I} \underline{\mathbf{h}}_q \underline{\mathbf{h}}_q^H$$

The interest of this new definition of the array factor directivity can be observed in (19.a). In consequence, the new array factor directivity is derived from the maximum eigenvalue of the generalized singular value decomposition of the numerator and the denominator of (19.b) minus one.

$$D_{RD} + 1 = \frac{P_T^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{b}} + |\underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d|^2}{P_T^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{b}} + \underline{\mathbf{b}}^H \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I \underline{\mathbf{b}}} \quad (19.a)$$

$$(\underline{\mathbf{P}}_T^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{I}} + \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d^H) \underline{\mathbf{b}} = \lambda (\underline{\mathbf{P}}_T^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{I}} + \underline{\mathbf{R}}_I) \underline{\mathbf{b}} \quad (19.b)$$

This last expression (19.a), reads, with $\log_2(\cdot)$, as the mutual information delivered to a receiver at the intended location, minus the mutual information delivered to NI receivers cooperating at the unintended locations with used power at the transmitter equal to P_T divided by the number of receivers. Thus, maximizing (18) entails to minimize the information delivered to the unintended locations with respect to the mutual information towards the desired one. In summary, the new definition is rooted on maximum achievable rates instead of on virtual SINR.

In order to get more insight, let us assume that N_I is equal to one and the channel to the unintended location is $\underline{\mathbf{h}}_i$, the generalized eigenvalues λ of (19.b) satisfy the following equation (see equation (A.7) in the appendix):

$$1 = \Phi(\lambda) = \frac{\lambda P_T h_i^2 \rho}{P_T h_d^2 + (1 - \lambda)} + \frac{\lambda P_T h_i^2 (1 - \rho)}{(1 - \lambda)} \quad (20)$$

with $h_d^2 = \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d$, $h_i^2 = \underline{\mathbf{h}}_i^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_i$, $\rho = \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{h}}_d^H \underline{\mathbf{h}}_i|^2}{h_d^2 h_i^2}$

This function is always increasing with λ , has zeros at λ equal to zero and $1 + E_T h_d^2 (1 - \rho)$, and a single pole at $1 + E_T h_d^2$. An example of the shape of this function is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Function $\Phi(\lambda)$, showing the two zeros and two poles. Bound for the maximum eigenvalue between the greatest zero and pole, i.e. including the largest value of λ for which $\Phi(\lambda)$ is equal to one.

From (20), as it is depicted in Figure 1, the maximum eigenvalue of (19), which is equal to the directivity (18) plus one, is bounded as it is shown in (21).

$$1 + h_d^2 P_T (1 - \rho) \lambda_{\max} \leq 1 + P_T h_d^2 \quad (21)$$

$$P_T h_d^2 (1 - \rho) \leq D_{RD, \max} \leq P_T h_d^2$$

Note that the maximum of this directivity is bounded by the same value of D_{VSNR} . At the same time, it can be observed that the maximum directivity, achieved when using the maximum

generalized eigenvector of the Rayleigh quotient (19), is always positive, i.e. no retro-directivity is present for the optimum beamformer. In addition, it is easy to check that for coincident locations of the intended and the unintended locations the directivity is zero. The maximum value in (21) is achieved when the intended channel is orthogonal to the unintended one.

The previous bounds, derived for a single interfered location can be extended for any number n_I of locations. In this case, function $\Phi(\lambda)$ is as (22), where d_q are the eigenvalues of the average interference matrix and n_T is the number of antenna elements of the array.

The function is always decreasing with λ and the greatest pole is located at $1/(P_T d_{\min} + 1)$. Above this pole is the value of λ for which the function is equal to one, i.e. the optimum λ . In consequence the directivity is greater than this values minus one.

$$\Phi(\lambda) = \sum_{q=1}^{n_I} \frac{|v_q|^2 P_T}{(P_T d_q + 1) \lambda - 1} \quad (22)$$

with

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & v_q & \dots & v_{n_I} \end{bmatrix}^T = \underline{\mathbf{U}} \underline{\mathbf{h}}_d$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}}_I = (\text{svd}(\underline{\mathbf{R}}_I)) = \underline{\mathbf{U}} \underline{\mathbf{D}} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^H$$

In addition, the function $\Phi(\lambda)$, for λ greater than one, can be bounded as (23).

$$\Phi(\lambda) \leq \sum_{q=1}^{n_I} \frac{|v_q|^2 P_T}{(E_T d_{\min} + 1) \lambda - 1} = \frac{P_d^2 E_T}{(\lambda - 1) + \lambda P_T d_{\min}} \leq \frac{h_d^2 P_T}{\lambda - 1} \quad (23)$$

Therefore, by using λ equal to $1 + P_T h_d^2$ in (23), it can be concluded that the function is below one. Since the function, for λ greater than one, is monotonically decreasing (24) results.

$$\Phi\left(\lambda = \frac{1}{1 + P_T d_{\min}}\right) \geq \Phi(\lambda_{\text{opt}}) = 1 \geq \Phi(1 + P_T h_d^2) \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{1}{1 + P_T d_{\min}} \leq \lambda_{\text{opt}} = D_{RD, \max} + 1 \leq 1 + P_T h_d^2$$

$$\frac{-P_T d_{\min}}{1 + P_T d_{\min}} \leq D_{RD, \max} \leq P_T h_d^2$$

The bounds shown in the last expression of (24) generalize the bounds shown in (21). Note that when the number of interferers is lower than the number of antennas of the array, the minimum eigenvalue of the interference matrix will be zero. This indicates that for rank deficient interference matrix there is not retro-directivity when using the optimum beamformer, i.e. the maximum eigenvector of (19.b). On the other hand, when the number of unintended locations is greater than the number of antennas of the array, then retro-directivity may appear making the maximum directivity negative, i.e. the average power experienced at the unintended locations can be greater than the power experienced at the desired location. The upper bound does not change with the number of interfered

locations in the scenario. It is worth remark that to achieve this upper bound it is necessary that the null-space of the interference matrix is not empty, i.e. the number of antennas have to be greater than the number of unintended locations.

It is remarkable that this new array factor directivity effectively goes to zero when the location of the intended coincides with the un-intended one. This was not the case for D_{VSNR} .

Finally, the dependence of the new directivity factor on the used power for transmission can be questionable, since traditional array factor directivity was independent of it, as expected for a directivity factor. Second, it is intuitive that directivity cannot depend of the path loss factor, in other words, array factor directivity should not change if the path loss factor is multiplied for the same value at all the locations. These two comments force to re-write the proposed directivity as (25); where α^2 is the path loss from the transmitter, with a single element to the desired location. Note that this modification precludes changes on the directivity when all locations increase or decrease simultaneously their path loss with respect to the transmitter site.

$$D_{\text{RD}} = \frac{|\underline{b}^H \underline{h}_d|^2 - \underline{b}^H \underline{R}_i \underline{b}}{\alpha^2 \underline{b}^H \underline{b} + \underline{b}^H \underline{R}_i \underline{b}} \quad (25)$$

Furthermore, the factor α^2 can be defined in terms of the quotient between the power received P_{Rd} , at the intended location divided by the used power P_{T} for a single antenna, as it is shown in (26). This notion of the path-loss was used in [6] for a different scenario dealing with decentralized beamforming for regulated interference channel.

$$P_{\text{T}} |\underline{h}_d|^2 = P_{\text{R}} \quad \alpha^2 = |\underline{h}_d|^2 / n_{\text{T}} = P_{\text{Rd}} / P_{\text{T}} \quad (26)$$

V. SIMULATIONS

This section provides some simulations that support the superiority of the proposed array factor directivity.

The tested definitions are basically the D_{VSNR} and the D_{RDE} . Traditional directivity is not included in the graphics, since it does not include any penalty for interfering pre-defined locations. Also, the D_{RD} cannot be properly compared due to its unbounded character. The two directivities included in the simulation are re-written below for the sake of clarity.

$$D_{\text{RD}} = \frac{|\underline{b}^H \underline{h}_d|^2 - \underline{b}^H \underline{R}_i \underline{b}}{\alpha^2 \underline{b}^H \underline{b} + \underline{b}^H \underline{R}_i \underline{b}} \quad (27)$$

$$D_{\text{VSNR}} = \frac{|\underline{b}^H \underline{h}_d|^2}{\alpha^2 \underline{b}^H \underline{b} + \underline{b}^H \underline{R}_i \underline{b}}$$

$$\text{with } \alpha^2 = |\underline{h}_d|^2 / n_{\text{T}}$$

The scenario considered will be the LOS scenario and, in consequence the channel vectors will be the steering-vectors of the locations with respect to the phase center of the transmitting array. This implies that α^2 parameter will be always one.

In the directivity plots, the beamformers under test are the optimizers of D_{RDE} and D_{VSNR} , together with the zero-forcing beamformer, which is the optimizer of D_{RD} . These

beamformers are reproduced in (28) as the solutions of a generalized eigenvalue problem, regardless VSNR and ZF have a closed form.

$$\begin{aligned} (\underline{I} + \underline{h}_d \underline{h}_d^H) \underline{b}_{\text{RDE}} &= \lambda_{1, \text{max}} (\underline{I} + \underline{R}_i) \underline{b}_{\text{RDE}} \\ (\underline{h}_d \underline{h}_d^H) \underline{b}_{\text{VSNR}} &= \lambda_{2, \text{max}} (\underline{I} + \underline{R}_i) \underline{b}_{\text{VSNR}} \\ (\underline{h}_d \underline{h}_d^H) \underline{b}_{\text{ZF}} &= \lambda_{1, \text{max}} (\underline{R}_i) \underline{b}_{\text{ZF}} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Figure 2 shows the major differences among these beamformer for a scenario with a single unintended location at -1.5 degrees of the desired location. The desired location is the broadside of a 10 antennas uniform linear array (ULA).

Since all the beamformers behave similar at locations that are well separated, in order to observe differences it is necessary to use scenarios with at least one unintended location very close to the intended one. In these scenarios it can be observed that the VSNR is unable to remove the interference. Meanwhile, the ZF beamformer removes completely the interference at the expense of reduced power delivered at the intended location. The RDE beamformer shows a tradeoff between the VSNR and the ZF beamforming, i.e. more interference attenuation to the interference than the VSNR, but more power delivered to the intended location than the ZF. It is worth remind that RDE maximizes the mutual information for the desired location versus the interfered location.

Figure 2 Beamformers' responses for a 10-antenna ULA array. Desired signal is at 0° and the un-intended location is at -1.5° .

Figure 2 shows the evolution of D_{VSNR} , for the same ULA array used in the previous figure, versus the location of the unintended location. The intended is located at the broadside of the aperture. The unintended location varies from -3 degrees up to -0.1 degrees. Note that the VSNR beamformer, the optimizer of this directivity shows the best performance.

Figure 3 D_{VSNR} performance for 3 beamformers (VSNR, ZF and RDE), versus the separation of the unintended and intended location for a 10-antenna ULA.

This figure evidences the major drawback of this directivity, which is that it does not go to zero when the angles of departure are the same, i.e. when the intended and unintended locations coincide. This comes from the fact that D_{VSNR} is not a proper measure of directivity.

Finally Figure 3, shows the performance of D_{RDE} , for the same scenario that was used in Figure 2. Now, all the beamformers converge to zero directivity when both positions coincide, and, of course the maximum performance is experienced for the optimizer beamformer.

Figure 4 D_{RDE} performance for 3 beamformers (VSNR, ZF and RDE), versus the separation of the unintended location for a 10-antenna ULA array.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A new definition for array factor directivity has been introduced. With this new definition proper beamforming for transmission can be obtained from its maximization. The new definition is based, differently from the traditional virtual signal to noise plus interference alternative, in the

maximization of the mutual information for the intended location with respect to the mutual information to the unintended ones. This basis is more solid than that of the so-called virtual SNR. In addition, the new directivity includes the notion of retro-directivity, i.e. negative directivity. Retro-directivity occurs when the average power delivered to the unintended locations is greater than the power delivered to the intended one. As a consequence, the proposed directivity goes to zero when desired and undesired locations coincide. To sum up, the new directivity reported stays above the traditional directivity for interference-dominated scenarios in all respects.

APPENDIX

The generalized eigenvalues of (A.1) can be bounded thanks to the structure of the matrix of the left side of the equation.

$$\left(P_T^{-1} I + h_d h_d^H \right) \underline{b} = \lambda \left(P_T^{-1} I + h_i h_i^H \right) \underline{b} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The eigenvectors matrix and eigenvalues of the left term matrix are:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(P_T^{-1} I + h_d h_d^H \right) &= \underline{U} \underline{D} \underline{U}^H \\ \underline{U} &= [h_d / h_d^2, P_{\perp h_d}] \\ \underline{D} &= \text{diag}(h_d^2 + P_T^{-1}, P_T^{-1}, \dots, P_T^{-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Note that the maximum eigenvector is the interfered location vector, and the rest of eigenvectors are orthogonal to it. In addition, the desired location vector can be written as (A.3).

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{h}_i &= \underline{U} \underline{v} \quad \text{or} \quad \underline{v} = \underline{U}^H \underline{h}_i \\ |\underline{v}|^2 &= h_i^2 \\ |\underline{v}(1)|^2 &= h_d^2 / h_d^2 \Rightarrow \sum_{q=2}^{n_r} |\underline{v}(q)|^2 = h_i^2 - (h_d^2 / h_d^2) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\text{with } h_d^2 = h_d^H h_d \quad h_i^2 = |h_d^H h_i|^2$$

Using (A.2) and (A.3) in (A.1), (A.4) results.

$$\underline{U} \underline{D} \underline{U}^H \underline{b} = \lambda \underline{U} \left(P_T^{-1} I + \underline{W}^H \right) \underline{U}^H \underline{b} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\underline{D} \underline{e} = \left(\lambda P_T^{-1} I + \lambda \underline{W}^H \right) \underline{e} \quad \text{with} \quad \underline{e} = \underline{U}^H \underline{b}$$

Since all the matrixes involved in (A.4) are diagonal, it is easy to arrange terms in (A.4) as indicated in (A.5).

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda \underline{W}^H \underline{e} &= \left(\underline{D} - \lambda P_T^{-1} I \right) \underline{e} \\ \lambda \left(\underline{D} - \lambda P_T^{-1} I \right)^{-1} \underline{W}^H \underline{e} &= \underline{e} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\underline{v}^H \lambda \left(\underline{D} - \lambda P_T^{-1} I \right)^{-1} \underline{v} = 1$$

The last equation in (A.5) can be written in terms of the components of vector \underline{v} and the diagonal entries of the matrix as (A.6).

$$1 = \sum_{q=1}^{n_r} \frac{\lambda |\underline{v}(q)|^2}{d_q - \lambda P_T^{-1}} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Finally, using that the eigenvalues after the first one are equal, together with that the first component of vector \underline{v} and its norm can be expressed as it is shown in (A.2), the functional

relationship that the generalized eigenvalues satisfy is (A.7).

$$1 = \Phi(\lambda)$$

$$\Phi(\lambda) = \frac{\lambda P_1 h_1^2 \rho}{P_1 h_1^2 + (\lambda - 1)} + \frac{\lambda P_1 h_1^2 (1 - \rho)}{(\lambda - 1)} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\rho = \frac{h_d^2}{h_g^2 h_1^2}$$

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